

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF TEACHERS IN ENGLISH MEDIATED INSTRUCTION FOR CHALLENGED LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the challenges and adaptations encountered by teachers implementing English-Mediated Instruction (EMI) with challenged learners at Calinog National Comprehensive High School. Thematic analysis of narratives from EMI ensures participant confidentiality while revealing key themes: teacher frustration, adaptation of instructional strategies, and the dedication required to meet diverse student needs. The research highlights the challenges associated with language barriers in EMI classrooms, where student comprehension difficulties can lead to teacher frustration. However, the study also underscores teachers' resilience and adaptability. Themes of instructional strategy adaptation include creating engaging and inclusive learning environments, utilizing technology-based methods, and implementing differentiated instruction. The research acknowledges the impact of time constraints, preparation demands, and the emotional investment required by educators in these settings. Based on these findings, the study recommends two key strategies: EMI teachers should design instruction tailored to individual learning styles and needs. The "Engli-fy" program is suggested as a potential strategy for this purpose. School leadership should consider selecting EMI teachers with demonstrated pedagogical expertise, engaging teaching styles, and a high tolerance for diverse learner needs. By understanding the lived experiences of EMI teachers, this

research aims to contribute valuable insights to improve instructional practices and support teachers in overcoming barriers to learning for challenged learners. This study sets a foundation for future research by exploring the complexities of EMI classrooms and their impact on both teachers and students.

Keywords: *Lived Experiences, English Mediated Instruction (EMI), Challenged Learners*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines prioritizes education to build a globally competitive workforce, mandating a curriculum with English-Mediated Instruction (EMI) through the Enhanced Basic Education Act (RA 10533). However, this shift presents challenges for teachers, particularly at Calinog National Comprehensive High School, a school established in 1999 and considered the mother school for secondary education in its Hiligaynon-speaking municipality. Here, teachers navigate a multilingual environment where English, alongside Filipino as the national language, are used alongside Hiligaynon (the local first language) as academic languages (DepEd, RA 10533). This complexity is further amplified by the presence of challenged learners, as defined by the Department of Education (DepEd). These learners face various difficulties, including learning disabilities (NICHD, 2023), disadvantaged backgrounds, or physical, sensory, or intellectual impairments. The Phil-IRI assessment conducted at Calinog National Comprehensive High School during enrollment revealed 32 challenged learners, with 14 exhibiting significant cognitive delays.

Furthermore, the recent global pandemic has further disrupted the educational landscape (Celeste, 2024), forcing a rapid shift towards online and blended learning environments (UNESCO, 2023). This shift has likely exacerbated existing challenges faced by both teachers and challenged learners within EMI classrooms.

Research highlights the challenges of EMI for both teachers and learners, particularly in subject areas beyond languages (Chia et al., 2022; (Tang, 2020) ; (Pamon & Oco, 2024)). EMI teachers struggle to navigate multilingual environments, ensure student comprehension, and adapt traditional teaching methods (Macaro, 2018; Yuan, 2021; Tomlinson, 2001). Additionally, catering to challenged learners within EMI classrooms presents a unique set of obstacles (Abdi et al., 2013).

This research explores the lived experiences of EMI teachers at Calinog National Comprehensive High School. The researchers aim to understand the challenges they encounter when implementing EMI with learners facing diverse learning difficulties. Specifically, this study focuses on how teachers adapt instructional strategies and approaches to engage these learners within the EMI framework. The goal is to develop

strategies and support systems that can empower challenged learners, EMI teachers, and stakeholders to cater to the specific needs of this unique learning group.

These are the research questions that the researchers sought to answer:

1. What are the challenges encountered by teachers when implementing English Mediated Instruction (EMI) with learners facing diverse learning difficulties?
2. How do teachers adapt their instructional strategies and approaches within the EMI framework to effectively engage learners with diverse learning difficulties, and what factors influence their decisions in employing these adaptations?
3. What output can be developed and implemented to effectively support challenged learners within English Mediated Instruction (EMI) classrooms as derived from of this present investigation?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a narrative inquiry approach to investigate the lived experiences of teachers implementing English-Mediated Instruction (EMI) with challenged learners at Calinog National Comprehensive High School during the 2023-2024 academic year. Narrative inquiry was chosen for its ability to capture the subjective meanings teachers attribute to their experiences (Daiute, 2013). Narratives, whether oral or written, serve as powerful tools for expressing lived realities, making this approach ideal for exploring the complexities of teacher experiences in EMI classrooms (Polkinghorne, 1995).

Context and Participants

The study was conducted at Calinog National Comprehensive High School, the largest secondary school in the municipality with a dedicated section for challenged learners. Three Grade 7 teachers who handle subjects like Math, Science, and English in this specialized section participated in the study. These teachers have extensive experience in regular education but are navigating a new chapter in their careers by working with challenged learners. Their selection was based on their willingness to participate and their roles in delivering EMI instruction to challenged learners.

Data Collection

Data collection involved a combination of semi-formal interviews and casual conversations to gain insights into the teachers' experiences. Formal interviews followed a structured format with guided questions designed to elicit detailed responses. The iterative nature of these interviews ensured the collection of rich and accurate data. All interactions were audio-recorded to capture the nuances and subtleties of participant narratives.

Complementing the formal interviews, the researchers leveraged existing familiarity with the teachers to facilitate informal conversations. These casual discussions

focused on the teachers' experiences and explored strategies for tailoring instruction to the needs of challenged learners. The goal of these discussions was to supplement the teachers' pedagogical repertoire with creative and differentiated approaches suitable for diverse learning styles. Prior to commencing the research, ethical approvals were obtained from the relevant authorities. Participants were chosen using purposive sampling and provided informed consent through signed consent forms.

Data Analysis

Following the principles of narrative inquiry, the data analysis focused on identifying overarching themes present in the participants' experiences (Cresswell & Poth, 2018). An iterative process of engagement with the participants through interviews and conversations facilitated the uncovering of narratives underlying their lived experiences. Thematic analysis involved multiple interactions and visits, fostering an environment where participants could openly share their experiences. Recurring patterns and significant insights emerging from these interactions formed the basis for identifying common themes.

The semi-structured interviews provided a structured framework for participants to articulate their experiences, while casual conversations offered additional layers of understanding. The researcher's shared context with the participants in terms of grade level and department facilitated the interpretation and identification of themes. This shared perspective enhanced the depth of analysis, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities encountered by the teacher-participants in EMI classrooms.

RESULTS

Challenges Encountered by Teachers in English Mediated Instruction

Language Barriers

Language is the foundation of education, unlocking the door to new knowledge and fostering understanding. However, for students entering classrooms where the language of instruction differs from their native tongue, this doorway can transform into a formidable barrier. Imagine struggling to grasp complex concepts veiled in unfamiliar words. This is the reality for many students dealing with classrooms brimming with linguistic diversity.

Schools with English as the Medium of Instruction (EMI) face a constant struggle: how to find the right balance between teaching content and developing language skills (Lo, 2015). This challenge is especially significant for students who are still acquiring academic literacy in their native language while also developing their English proficiency. The problem is further compounded by the abstract and unfamiliar nature of the content being taught, particularly in subjects like science and mathematics (Lo, 2015).

The Zone of Proximal Development (Vygotsky, 1978) emphasizes the importance of scaffolding, where teachers provide temporary support to help students complete tasks beyond their independent capabilities. Language barriers can hinder this process by

limiting a teacher's ability to effectively explain concepts and assess a student's grasp of the material within their zone of proximal development (Vygotsky, 1978).

Additionally, the Background Knowledge Theory (Pearson & Graves, 1984) theory highlights the role of a learner's existing knowledge in understanding new information. Students with limited English proficiency may struggle to connect new concepts in the subject matter being taught to their existing knowledge base due to the language barrier, hindering their overall learning (Pearson & Graves, 1984).

The narratives from participants shed light on the significant challenges posed by language barriers in the context of English-mediated instruction. Across different subjects, participants expressed difficulties in comprehension, communication, and teaching due to varying levels of English proficiency among students.

Mr. Math whose journey is marked by the ever-present challenge of bridging linguistic divides in the pursuit of knowledge. Despite efforts to communicate with clarity using terms that are easily understood, a shadow looms over the classroom - the unsettling realization that not all students grasp the subtleties of English. Yet, amidst this uncertainty, there are glimmers of hope. T1 reflects on the diversity of comprehension among students; while some struggle to understand even the simplest English terms, others grasp them with ease. This revelation fuels T1's determination to tailor instruction to meet the unique needs of each learner.

Mr. Math: "So you know one of the barriers is language itself. Even though sometimes I use simple terms some cannot understand simple English. . on the other hand, however, some can understand but few can recognize them. That is why sometimes like I think and ponder what among other words they would understand and not understand and then sometimes it takes time to think about that. That is why sometimes I need to talk to them in a way that I will know what words they are familiar with and not familiar with, that they may have encountered most likely the words if they hear the familiar words they could recall the meaning. There are some words they could read and understand but they do not understand the meaning of the words. It could be translated in Kinaray-a, Hiligaynon, and sometimes we use the Tagalog language.

Miss Science also faces a formidable challenge in bridging the gap between English terminology and local comprehension. With each lesson, T2 confronts the stark reality that many students struggle to grasp even the simplest of English terms. The frustration is intense as T2 pours heart and soul into crafting lessons that resonate with every student. Yet, despite relentless efforts, the disconnect persists. Determined to break through this barrier, T2 traverse on a linguistic journey, translating complex scientific concepts into a mix of languages - Kinaray-a, Tagalog, and English.

Miss Science: They can't even read and comprehend simple English terms. I have to translate them into Kinaray-a, Tagalog, and English just to accommodate the language, especially in Science. Some terms cannot be translated into the local language.

Mrs. English steps into the shoes of an English Remedial Reading Teacher, ready to face the daunting task ahead. At the heart of Mrs. English's narrative lies the realization that the first barrier to be surmounted is the students' proficiency in the language itself.

As Mrs. English begins teaching remedial reading, it becomes clear that many students struggle with basic literacy skills like phonetic sounds and recognizing letters. With determination, Mrs. English faces this tough challenge directly. Each lesson offers hope, guiding students toward language skills. Yet, despite successes, the road ahead remains steep.

Mrs. English: "As the English Remedial Reading Teacher, the first barrier is their proficiency in the language. They can't even produce basic phonetic sounds, and some of them cannot identify most letters of the alphabet or how to produce these sounds."

This challenge on language barrier is supported by several research results and theories. For instance, a study by Chia et al. (2022) identified language barrier as a major hurdle for teachers. It hinders effective communication with students and restricts their ability to explain concepts clearly.

According to a study by Tang (2020), the fluency of both teachers and learners plays a critical role in the success of English-based instruction. Language difficulties can lead to confusion, frustration, and hinder student participation (Tang, 2020).

A recent study by Pamon and Oco (2024) emphasizes the difficulties teachers face when explaining complex ideas and evaluating student knowledge in classrooms where English is the main language of instruction, especially if students have a limited grasp of English.

Founder of "Basic Education", Bestor (1956) contended that educational institutions ought to furnish students with a robust foundation in the core modes of cognition encompassed by disciplines such as history, science, mathematics, literature, language, and art. These disciplines, which have evolved from humanity's quest for cultural insight, intellectual acumen, and practical knowledge, are vital components of a comprehensive education (Smith, 2020). But these foundations should be part of the elementary level of these learners, yet they reach the secondary level missing these core foundations.

Language barriers present a significant hurdle within the classroom, hindering clear communication, effective assessment, and the ability to build upon existing knowledge. These roadblocks impede the very foundation of education – fostering understanding and cultivating well-rounded individuals. By recognizing these challenges and implementing strategies to overcome the language barrier, educators can empower all students to understand the fundamental concepts of different subjects, unlocking their full potential within the diverse landscape of education.

Teachers Frustrations and Self Doubt in Facilitating Learning

The sterile image of a classroom often portrays a one-way transmission of knowledge – a teacher imparting wisdom to eager young minds. However, the reality within those walls can be far more nuanced. The frustrations of educators who tirelessly grapple with the persistent challenge of ensuring their students not only grasp but deeply connect with the material, resonate deeply within the context of teaching and learning in English mediated classrooms.

Each participant's narrative reflects a common thread of doubt, frustration, and self-reflection regarding their effectiveness as educators in overcoming the barriers to learning faced by their students. A deeper understanding of the unseen battles waged within classrooms can be gained through their struggles, highlighting the dedication and emotional investment poured into their craft by educators.

In the math class, Teacher T1 faces a big problem: not knowing if students understand the lessons. Every time he teaches, he worries if the students really get it. This makes him feel frustrated and unsure about his teaching.

Mr. Math: This sometimes gives me doubt whether they have fully grasped my delivery or the way I deliver instructions.

Miss Science also faces a big frustration: students struggling to understand even the simplest lessons. Despite putting in lots of effort to make the lessons clear, T2 feels disappointed when students still find it hard to understand and express themselves.

Miss Science: It was frustrating in my part as a teacher because after giving all my efforts in order for these learners to digest the lesson even a very simple activity but then they have difficulty in understanding and expressing themselves.

Mrs. English shares a common struggle: feeling frustrated and questioning their teaching skills. When students struggle to learn, Mrs. English wonders how to better help them. Mrs. English shares her experience to understand the challenges teachers face in supporting students' English learning journey.

Mrs. English: It made me re-evaluate my teaching abilities and it frustrates me on how to effectively help them in their learning endeavors.

Given the above situations, teachers may encounter difficulties regarding their own recognition and comprehension of Language Learning Strategies (LLS). They might lack familiarity with various strategies and struggle with effectively incorporating them into their language teaching (Pawlak, 2019). When employing English as the medium of instruction (EMI), instructors might encounter difficulties in evaluating students' comprehension and progress. This may necessitate the creation of assessment techniques and instruments that are in harmony with EMI principles (Ernawati et al., 2021).

Educators might experience frustrations linked to their own linguistic competence. The document notes that certain teachers resort to utilizing the local first language (L1) to elucidate meanings as required (Sahan et al., 2022).

The idealized image of classroom learning as a simple knowledge transfer crumbles under the weight of educators' everyday frustrations. Teachers grapple with ensuring student comprehension and engagement, facing challenges that lead to self-doubt and a constant process of reflection. The limitations of traditional learning theories, like Behaviorism and Social Learning Theory, highlight the need for methods that foster intrinsic motivation and cater to individual student needs.

Extracts from Math, Science, and English teachers further illuminate these frustrations, showcasing their struggles with student understanding and their own teaching effectiveness. The complexities of using English as the medium of instruction (EMI) add another layer of challenge, demanding specialized strategies and resources for effective assessment.

Ultimately, this exploration of teacher frustrations underscores their dedication and emotional investment. While they face unseen battles within the classroom, their tireless efforts highlight the crucial role they play in nurturing young minds.

There are also theories that support the results of the study. Behaviorism (B.F. Skinner, 1976) emphasizes shaping desired behaviors through rewards and punishments. While effective for specific skills, it can be frustrating for teachers who struggle to engage students intrinsically or want to foster critical thinking beyond rote memorization.

Social Learning Theory (Bandura 1977) focuses on learning through observation and imitation. Teacher frustration can stem from limited resources for creating engaging learning environments or a lack of support for individualized instruction.

Time and Preparation Constraints

Teachers face time constraints and increased workload when preparing lessons tailored to individual learning difficulties. This is exacerbated by additional teaching responsibilities and limited preparation time, leading to frustration and exhaustion.

The need for creative and engaging activities to support comprehension and retention adds to the burden of lesson planning, requiring innovative approaches to meet the diverse needs of learners effectively.

For Mr. Math teaching is tough work. He spends a lot of time planning lessons to fit the needs of all his students. Planning takes up a lot of his time and energy. Even on weekends, he is still working late to get everything ready. And when lessons go on for weeks, it is hard to come up with fun activities. Mr. Math's journey is a story of hard work and determination to give his students the best education possible.

Mr. Math: I have to design and think what to teach every single day/week... The lesson preparation is taking a toll on me, it eats my time... Most of the time, I have to use my weekend and go home late just to advance some of the preparations for the specific need of the class... Lesson preparations that will cater

individual learning difficulties... most cases our lessons last a week to two, that gives me difficulty to think creative activities that I know will fit each of the needs.

For Miss Science, where every word holds weight. She carefully considers which words her students will understand, often spending time pondering over each one. Translating lessons into local language adds another layer of complexity to her already busy schedule. Miss Science's experiences reflect her dedication to adapting instruction to meet the diverse linguistic needs of their students, showcasing the additional time and effort required to ensure effective learning.

Miss Science mentions the time-consuming process of considering which words students would understand and translating lessons into local languages.

Miss Science: That is why sometimes I think and ponder what among other words they would understand and not understand and then sometimes it takes time to think about that.

This indicates the additional time and effort required to adapt instruction to meet the diverse linguistic needs of students.

For Mrs. English, the quest for engaging learning never ends. While she may not directly mention time constraints, her focus on captivating activities like guessing games and videos speaks volumes. It hints at the challenge of balancing preparation time with the need to keep students interested and attentive. Her journey is a proof to her creativity and dedication to making learning enjoyable, even amidst the pressures of limited time.

Mrs. English indirectly references time constraints and the need for engaging activities to support learning.

Mrs. English: What I'm always doing was to give them a more interesting activity like guessing game or videos because they're more attentive with these kinds of activities."

While not explicitly stating time constraints, the emphasis on finding engaging activities suggests the pressure to maintain student engagement amidst limited preparation time.

English Medium Instruction (EMI) presents unique challenges for teachers, particularly regarding time constraints and workload. As Macaro (2018) found in her study, teachers often struggle with limited preparation time. This stems from the need to adapt materials and activities to cater to the diverse learning styles and needs present in EMI classrooms. Macaro's research highlights the additional effort required for EMI teachers to ensure all students can comprehend the content being delivered in a non-native language. This resonates with the narrative of Mr. Math, who spends significant time planning lessons to fit the needs of his students, often working late and on weekends.

Yuan (2021) investigated the link between the pressure to adapt instruction in EMI classrooms and increased teacher stress and burnout. Their findings suggest that the

additional planning and time commitment required for EMI can lead to feelings of exhaustion and decreased well-being for educators.

Effectively differentiating instruction to meet the needs of all students is a complex endeavor in any classroom setting. However, the challenges are amplified in EMI contexts. Tomlinson (2001) explores these complexities in her book, "How to Differentiate Instruction in Mixed-Ability Classrooms." She emphasizes the significant time commitment required to design and implement effective differentiated instruction strategies.

According to Wood and McCarthy (2002) in their book "Understanding and Preventing Teacher Burnout," the pressure to address each student's individual needs is a major source of stress for educators. This challenge becomes even more pronounced in EMI (English Medium Instruction) classrooms due to the added complexity of language learning. The experiences of Mr. Math and Miss Science illustrate these difficulties. Mr. Math faces the struggle of providing for students with different learning paces within limited time constraints. Miss Science describes the extra time it takes to adapt lessons and find the right vocabulary to ensure all students with varying language skills can understand the material.

While creative and engaging activities are crucial for fostering language acquisition in EMI settings, developing such activities presents a significant challenge for teachers (Lyster, 2007). Lyster acknowledges the difficulties teachers face in designing engaging lessons within limited preparation time. This is particularly relevant for Mrs. English, who, although not explicitly mentioning time constraints, focuses on incorporating engaging activities like guessing games and videos to maintain student interest (see original text). Her approach reflects the need for creativity in EMI classrooms but also hints at the underlying pressure to balance this with limited preparation time.

Gu (2003) explores the concept of scaffolding in language learning, where teachers provide temporary support to students until they can learn independently. This approach, while effective, necessitates additional planning and creativity from the teacher. The time constraints faced by EMI teachers can make it challenging to implement scaffolding strategies effectively.

The research and theories presented here provide a strong foundation for understanding the challenges faced by EMI teachers. Time constraints, increased workload, the complexities of differentiation, and the pressure to create engaging activities all contribute to the demanding nature of EMI instruction. The narratives of Mr. Math, Miss Science, and Mrs. English further illustrate these challenges and the dedication of EMI teachers who strive to provide effective learning experiences for their students despite the constraints they face.

Teachers' Adaption of Instructional Strategies and Approaches

Creating an Engaging and Inclusive Learning Environment

Creating a truly engaging and inclusive learning environment in an English Medium Instruction (EMI) classroom is a complex but rewarding challenge. Educators face a diverse range of student needs, from varying levels of English proficiency to individual learning difficulties.

Mr. Math: I use some visuals, usually illustrations, and of course repetition for emphasis. Like first I'll show it to them then for quite some time, I'll repeat it again and again. Sometimes it can be three to four times or five times repetition. ...sometimes I let their classmates teach them related to the lesson that transpired that they need to recall. Well, usually they have the same difficulty most likely they have the same language I can barely relate...if their classmates or peer explain the how's or concepts to them to the language that they could understand information or instruction given to them...Usually in PowerPoint I use animation. I could easily get their attention. I somehow notice that some of them has this short span of attention that is why now I use strategies/ technologies to get their attention.

For Miss Science, innovation and engagement take center stage. In science education, Miss Science employs a variety of creative strategies to capture the attention of her students with diverse learning needs. She kickstarts her lessons with a captivating 3-4 letter words spelling bee, setting the stage for interactive learning from the get-go. Harnessing the power of technology, Miss Science utilizes videos and emojis to foster active participation and enhance comprehension. Recognizing the limitations some students face with access to gadgets, they ingeniously curate a compilation of video lessons and activity sheets, ensuring every student has access to valuable educational resources.

Miss Science: When I started handling these groups, I started with 3-4 letter words spelling bee in my science class...I used videos, emojis for guessing the word/words since they are more attentive in activities like these.... Since most of the learners do not have gadget, instead I made a compilation of video lesson, videos from You tube as a form of teaching instructions and some downloaded activity sheets related to the lessons intended for every quarter.

For Mrs. English, every lesson is a journey of discovery tailored to the unique needs of each student. In English remedial education, Mrs. English embraces a learner-centered approach, prioritizing the individual capacities and learning levels of her students over predefined objectives set by the department. With her dedication, she crafts new learning activities and worksheets that cater specifically to the diverse needs of her students, ensuring meaningful and impactful learning experiences.

Mrs. English: With this unique group, I have to embrace to the learner centered approach. Instead of targeting the objective based set by the department, I have to focus on the learner's capacity and level of learning, I have to start from

there. Then, I craft new learning activities and worksheets that will suit their learning needs...

The importance of social interaction and collaboration in learning draws on the ideas of Lev Vygotsky (Alkhudiry, 2022). Vygotsky's concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) highlights that learning is most effective when students receive scaffolding and support from more knowledgeable peers or teachers (Alkhudiry, 2022). This theory fosters a sense of belonging and community in the classroom, ultimately promoting inclusivity.

Stage-learning theory of development (Piaget, 1952) proposes that children view the world differently than adults. This is because they are constantly reconstructing and repatterning their understanding of reality as they progress through distinct developmental stages. As a result, children's grasp of the world often clashes with the curriculum and instruction typically imposed by adults.

Early childhood and elementary education, according to Ornstein et al. (2011), should instead be centered on how children develop and learn on their own terms. This means acknowledging that children have their own unique readiness for new learning, based on the cognitive level they've reached in their specific stage of development.

According to Gardner (1983), the Multiple Intelligences theory (MI) posits that individuals possess various learning domains, emphasizing that intelligence extends beyond the traditional IQ measurements. Gardner suggests that these intelligences emerge through individuals' engagement in culturally valued activities, fostering distinctive cognitive patterns (Gardner, 1983). This paradigm shift has spurred substantial research and educational initiatives, challenging educators to reconsider conventional notions of learning and intellect (Ornstein, Levine, & Gerald Lee Gutek, 2011)

Abdi, Laei, and Ahmadyan (2013) assert that a notable contrast exists in the academic performance of students instructed through Multiple Intelligences-based teaching strategies compared to those taught via traditional methods. Those exposed to MI-based approaches demonstrate higher levels of success relative to their counterparts educated conventionally.

Mphahlele and Korkmaz (2023) highlight the potential of technology integration to overcome social and access barriers in education. They emphasize that technology offers avenues for active, self-directed learning and collaborative experiences, thereby enhancing student engagement. Moreover, technology facilitates broader access to educational materials, fostering participation and encouraging creativity among learners.

Teachers adapting instructional strategies in EMI classrooms face the challenge of creating an engaging and inclusive environment for a diverse range of learners.

Utilization of Technology-Based Instructional Strategies

The utilization of technology-based instructional strategies represents a significant advancement in modern pedagogy, particularly within the context of English Mediated

Instruction (EMI) classrooms. Teachers are increasingly leveraging technological tools such as PowerPoint presentations, multimedia materials, and interactive software to enhance engagement and enrich learning experiences for students with diverse learning needs.

One of the primary ways in which technology is utilized in the EMI classroom is through the creation and utilization of PowerPoint presentations. These presentations offer teachers a dynamic platform to deliver content in a visually stimulating manner. By incorporating images, diagrams, and animations, teachers can effectively convey complex concepts and information in a way that is both engaging and comprehensible to students.

For Mr. Math's classroom, innovation and engagement are at the forefront of every lesson. With a keen eye for leveraging technology to enhance learning experiences, Mr. Math utilizes PowerPoint presentations as a basis of his instructional approach. Through the strategic use of animation and colorful illustrations, he effortlessly captures the attention of his students, ensuring that even those with short attention spans remain fully engaged.

Recognizing the diverse needs and learning preferences of his students, Mr. Math employs a range of strategies and technologies to maintain their focus and foster active participation. By incorporating dynamic visuals and interactive elements into his PowerPoint presentations, he creates a dynamic and immersive learning environment that appeals to the senses and stimulates curiosity.

Mr. Math: I usually use PowerPoint. I use animation. I could easily get their attention. I somehow notice that some of them has this short span of attention that is why now I use strategies/ technologies to get their attention. Most likely illustrations, colorful illustrations

Miss Science employs a variety of engaging instructional strategies to captivate their attention and enhance their understanding of scientific concepts.

Utilizing the power of multimedia, Miss Science integrates videos and emojis into her lessons to promote active participation and comprehension. By leveraging visual and interactive elements, she ensures that her students remain fully engaged and eager to participate in classroom activities. Whether it is through video clips that bring scientific concepts to life or emojis that make learning fun and interactive, Miss Science goes above and beyond to make her lessons memorable and impactful.

Recognizing the challenges posed by limited access to technology, Miss Science ingeniously curates a compilation of video lessons and activity sheets to ensure that all students have access to valuable educational resources. By sourcing videos from platforms like YouTube and creating downloadable activity sheets, she ensures that every student has the opportunity to learn and succeed, regardless of their access to gadgets.

Miss Science: I used videos, emojis for guessing the word/words since they are more attentive in activities like these.... Since most of the learners do not have gadget, instead I made a compilation of video lessons, videos from You tube as a

form of teaching instructions and some downloaded activity sheets related to the lessons intended for every quarter.

For Mrs. English, harnessing the power of technology, Teacher 3 integrates ICT (Information and Communication Technology) seamlessly into her instruction. Through interactive models and graphic presentations, she facilitates oral production of words and reading, engaging students in active participation and comprehension. Believing in the transformative potential of multimedia learning, Mrs. English utilizes PowerPoint presentations to create a dynamic and engaging learning environment. Recognizing the youthful energy of her students, she infuses each lesson with music and movement, keeping their interest piqued and their enthusiasm ignited.

Mrs. English: With the advent of technology, like PowerPoints, it somehow eases my lesson delivery... Since it is mostly oral production of words or reading, I use Models as I teach with ICT integrations. I have to read aloud words and they repeat it after me. I believe that teachers are the greatest multimedia a learner can have with the extra aid of technology...I use PowerPoint, music, and dance integration. They are still kids and they liked making fun around. Adding music keeps their interest up to the beat.

The integration of technology-based instructional strategies has become a prominent advancement in modern education, particularly for EMI classrooms. Research suggests that these tools can significantly enhance student engagement and cater to diverse learning styles.

Studies have shown that PowerPoint presentations, with their ability to incorporate images, diagrams, and animations, can effectively convey complex information in an engaging way for EMI students (Kurzweil, 2018). This aligns with Mr. Math's experience, where he utilizes animations and colorful illustrations to capture student attention, especially those with shorter attention spans.

Research by Xu (2017) suggests that multimedia elements like videos and emojis can be effective in promoting active participation and comprehension in EMI classrooms. This aligns with Miss Science's approach of integrating these elements into her lessons, potentially making scientific concepts more engaging and interactive for students with diverse language skills.

Furthermore, technology offers a solution for tailoring instruction to different learning styles. Shamshul et al. (2024) highlight how educators can use technology to create accessible learning materials, like downloadable activity sheets, that cater to students with limited access to home devices.

Studies by Moore, (2013) suggest that technology can create dynamic and interactive learning environments. This aligns with Mrs. English's use of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) tools like PowerPoint presentations to create a stimulating learning experience, incorporating elements like music and movement to keep students engaged

While the challenges faced by EMI teachers are undeniable, the narratives of Mr. Math, Miss Science, and Mrs. English also showcase their dedication and resourcefulness. Technology-based instructional strategies, as supported by research, offer powerful tools to address these challenges. By utilizing multimedia elements, interactive activities, and accessible resources, EMI teachers can create engaging and effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of their students. As educators continue to explore and integrate these advancements, EMI classrooms have the potential to become even more dynamic and successful in fostering language acquisition and a love of learning for all students.

Differentiated Instructions

Differentiated instruction is a pedagogical approach where teachers tailor their instructional methods, materials, and assessments to accommodate the diverse learning needs, abilities, and interests of students in the classroom (Tomlinson, 2014). This approach recognizes that students learn in various ways and at different paces, and thus, requires teachers to adapt their teaching strategies to ensure that all students have the opportunity to succeed. One aspect of differentiated instruction involves offering personalized learning opportunities to students based on their individual needs and abilities. This may include providing alternative assignments or projects that allow students to demonstrate their understanding of the material in a way that aligns with their strengths and interests. For example, a student who struggles with traditional written assignments may be given the option to create a multimedia presentation or participate in a hands-on activity instead.

Furthermore, differentiated instruction often involves creating activity sheets and learning materials that are tailored to individual abilities. Teachers may provide modified versions of assignments or worksheets that offer additional support or scaffolding for students who require it, while challenging those who are ready for more advanced work. By adjusting the complexity and level of difficulty of tasks, teachers can ensure that all students are appropriately challenged and engaged in their learning.

Differentiated instruction is evident throughout Mr. Math's teaching practices as he deals with the challenges of English-mediated instruction in mathematics for challenged learners. One of the key barriers he faces is the language itself, with students varying in their understanding of English terms. To address this, he employs various instructional strategies tailored to individual needs, such as translating terms into local languages and simplifying explanations. This personalized approach ensures that all students can comprehend the material despite their diverse linguistic backgrounds.

Mr. Math: I modify, like I mentioned earlier I translate it to the local language, localized terms... It is important that they participate prepared activities and understand its applications in real life. If they could grasp the concept of the lessons and utilize them on the practical way that they could use it and how important it is most likely they make effort to understand."

Furthermore, Mr. Math modifies his instructional approaches within the English-regulated framework to effectively engage learners with diverse learning difficulties. He

utilizes visual aids, repetition, and peer tutoring to reinforce concepts and accommodate different learning styles. For instance, he incorporates drawings and physical activities to illustrate mathematical concepts and keep students engaged. This approach not only caters to students' individual strengths but also fosters collaboration and peer support in the classroom.

Mr. Math: I use some visuals, usually illustrations, and of course repetition for emphasis... sometimes I let their classmates teach them related to the lesson that transpired.

On the other hand, Miss Science excerpts from narratives shed light on the implementation of differentiated instruction within the classroom setting, showcasing various strategies employed to accommodate the diverse learning needs of students.

Miss Science initiates the instructional process by conducting a 3-4 letter words spelling bee, recognizing the need to address fundamental phonetic skills. By focusing on individual phonetic development through one-on-one reading of alphabets and sounds, the teacher demonstrates a personalized approach tailored to the specific needs of each student. Additionally, incorporating hands-on activities, such as writing exercises and oral reading, not only enhances engagement but also reinforces learning through multisensory experiences. The inclusion of rewards for remarkable achievement further incentivizes student participation and reinforces positive learning outcomes.

Miss Science: When I started handling these group, I started with 3-4 letter words spelling bee. I've noticed that almost three-fourths of the class can hardly distinguish letters so I focused on phonetics first. One on one reading of the alphabets and sounds. Writing skills, oral reading, spelling, hands-on activities were some of the specific instructional strategies which I thought greatly helped in engaging learners. I even gave rewards for those with a remarkable achievement.

Lastly, Mrs. English acknowledges the diverse learning needs of her students and adopts a learner-centered approach. Instead of rigidly following predetermined objectives, she prioritizes understanding the capacity and level of learning of each student. This approach allows her to tailor their instruction to meet the specific needs of individual learners, ensuring a more effective and personalized learning experience.

Recognizing that one-size-fits-all approaches may not effectively engage students with diverse learning difficulties, the teacher takes initiative in developing their own learning activities and worksheets. These materials are designed to suit the unique needs and abilities of the students, incorporating elements such as mixed language, translation, and picture association to facilitate comprehension and retention of lesson content.

Understanding the importance of practice in reinforcing learning, the Mrs. English allocates time for students to practice and deliver basic words or concepts. This practice allows students to consolidate their understanding and mastery of the material, particularly for those who may struggle with certain concepts. By providing ample practice opportunities, the teacher supports students in overcoming learning difficulties and building confidence in their abilities.

Mrs. English: "With this unique group, I have to embrace the learner-centered approach... I have to focus on the learner's capacity and level of learning... Then, I develop my own learning activities and worksheets that will suit their learning need."

"I also give time for them to practice and deliver the set basic words... Mix language, translation, and picture association of each term/vocabulary."

Differentiated instruction is a cornerstone of effective teaching, especially in English Mediated Instruction (EMI) classrooms with students from diverse backgrounds. This approach, as defined by Tomlinson (2014), involves tailoring instruction to individual student needs, abilities, and interests. It acknowledges that students learn at different paces and in various ways, necessitating flexible teaching strategies to ensure all students have the opportunity to thrive.

Differentiation allows for personalized learning experiences based on individual needs and strengths. Students may be offered alternative assignments or projects that cater to their preferred learning styles, such as multimedia presentations or hands-on activities, as opposed to traditional written work (Tomlinson, 2001).

Creating differentiated learning materials is crucial. This may involve providing modified versions of assignments or worksheets with additional support for struggling students, while offering more challenging tasks for advanced learners (Heacox, 2008). Adjusting the complexity and difficulty level ensures appropriate challenge and engagement for all students.

Recognizing the challenges of English-mediated instruction for students with varying English proficiency, Mr. Math employs various strategies tailored to individual needs. He translates terms into local languages and simplifies explanations, ensuring comprehension for students with diverse linguistic backgrounds. This aligns with the concept of scaffolding, where temporary support is provided until students can learn independently (Gu, 2003).

Differentiated instruction offers a powerful framework for EMI teachers to create inclusive and effective learning environments. By tailoring instruction to individual needs, utilizing a variety of instructional strategies, and providing personalized support, EMI teachers can empower all students to succeed in their learning journey.

Proposed Teaching Strategies

Using the English language to enhance learning in various subjects, not just English itself is called "English." This strategic approach leverages the power of English to deepen understanding in disciplines such as math and science. The goal is to teach scientific and mathematical principles through the lens of English, using tailored learning strategies for each student. Englify recognizes students' diverse learning styles and incorporates various methods, such as visual aids, group discussions, and project-based learning, to cater to different preferences and ensure complete comprehension of real-life applications.

This intentional teaching design encourages the integration of subject knowledge and cross-curricular teaching. In this approach, English lessons incorporate the content taught in Mathematics and Science by subject teachers during the 4th quarter. It requires teachers to purposefully design lessons that utilize the strengths of both English and the target subject.

Conclusions

This study investigated the experiences of teachers in English-Mediated Instruction (EMI) classrooms. While language barriers and time constraints posed challenges, the teachers' dedication to student success was evident. They employed engaging and inclusive teaching methods, differentiated instruction, and technology-based strategies, demonstrating a commitment to best practices for EMI classrooms.

However, our findings also highlight key areas for improvement. Language barriers significantly hindered student comprehension. This emphasizes the need for targeted interventions that address individual language proficiency levels. Ensuring effective communication across all subjects is crucial for successful learning in EMI environments.

Teacher frustration with student engagement underscores the importance of implementing engaging teaching methods. Interactive activities and fostering a positive learning environment can boost motivation, leading to improved student performance.

Furthermore, differentiated lesson planning is essential for catering to diverse learning needs in EMI classrooms. However, time constraints present a significant barrier. Providing teachers with resources and support systems can help them manage time effectively and personalize instruction for each student.

This research introduces the ENGLI-FY teaching approach, specifically designed for EMI classrooms with learners with diverse needs. ENGLI-FY empowers teachers by enhancing their strategies and strengthening foundational English language skills. This approach offers a promising avenue for further research to investigate its effectiveness in improving learning outcomes across various subjects.

Overall, this study highlights the crucial role of teacher dedication and adaptable strategies in creating successful EMI classrooms. It emphasizes the importance of addressing language proficiency, fostering engagement, and providing time management support for teachers. By implementing these recommendations and exploring innovative approaches like ENGLI-FY, schools can create positive and successful learning environments for all students in EMI settings.

Recommendations

This study yielded valuable insights for improving student success in English-Mediated Instruction (EMI) classrooms.

EMI teachers can foster student engagement by tailoring lessons to individual needs and proficiency levels. This involves incorporating diverse strategies like visuals, interactive activities, and technology into lesson plans. Additionally, providing scaffolding techniques for students with lower English proficiency can significantly enhance

comprehension and participation. Teachers working with challenged learners can leverage Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles. UDL promotes presenting information in multiple formats and offering students choices in how they understand the material. Additionally, collaboration on Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) and employing differentiated instruction through adapted tasks and targeted support can create a positive and inclusive learning environment for all.

Regardless of classroom context (EMI or traditional), differentiated instruction is a key skill for future educators. Tailoring lessons with engaging visuals, activities, and technology caters to diverse student needs, learning styles, and proficiency levels. This personalized approach fosters deeper understanding and engagement for all students. Schools can significantly enhance EMI classrooms by allocating resources for developing high-quality learning materials. These materials should be designed with diverse learners in mind and bridge the gap between language acquisition and subject mastery. This ensures clear understanding regardless of a student's English proficiency level.

School leaders can play a crucial role in enhancing EMI classrooms by implementing initiatives to improve technology access and integration. This involves providing necessary hardware, software, and training for teachers on utilizing technology tools. These tools can be powerful assets for differentiated instruction and personalized learning experiences within EMI settings.

Finally, we encourage teachers to explore the implementation of the ENGLI-FY program specifically designed for EMI classrooms with diverse learners. This program equips teachers with effective strategies to bridge the language gap and create a more holistic learning environment that fosters success for all students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical integrity of this research study was paramount, guided by a commitment to uphold the highest standards of ethical conduct throughout all stages of the research process. Central to this commitment was the meticulous attention paid to ensuring the informed consent and confidentiality of all participants involved.

Prior to their involvement in the study, prospective participants were provided with comprehensive information regarding the research procedures, objectives, and potential implications of their participation. They were given the opportunity to ask questions and clarify any concerns before providing their voluntary consent to participate. This ensured that participants were fully aware of their rights and could make informed decisions regarding their involvement in the study.

Moreover, stringent measures were implemented to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of the participants. Two key ethical standards were upheld to protect participants' privacy: confidentiality and anonymity. Participants were assured that any information shared during the study would be treated with the utmost confidentiality, with identifying details kept strictly confidential and accessible only to those directly involved

in the research process. Additionally, the principle of anonymity was rigorously adhered to, ensuring that participants' identities remained undisclosed throughout the study. For the purpose of narrative coherence and confidentiality, pseudonyms were assigned to the participants. Mr. Math, Miss Science, and Mrs. English were chosen as pseudonyms, reflecting both their subject areas and maintaining anonymity. These titles accurately represent the participants' professional identities while preserving their privacy during the data analysis process.

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